

SOTECIN FACTORY

D6.2 Communication and Dissemination Plan and Progress (second version)

June 2023

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1. INTRODUCTION

This document is developed as part of the SoTeIn Factory project and it represents Deliverable 6.2 Communication and Dissemination Plan and Progress (second version). D6.2 aims to achieve the following objectives of Work Package 6:

- Ensuring pan-European exposure, adoption, and application of results.
- Defining the network stabilisation model for SoTeIn Factory.
- Realising synergies within the knowledge exchange through stabilised interconnections.

This document stands as the iteration of D6.1 (M3) and the update of its Communication and Dissemination Plan, called short CDP which provided a set of practical tools to be used by all SoTeIn Factory partners for ensuring an efficient communication and dissemination of the project activities and results among its target audiences through the most suitable channels for maximum impact. Therefore, this deliverable complements it with the strategy and action plan concerning the communication and dissemination activities to support the outputs of each work package alongside tools and channels, as well as the materials that are regularly used in the described style and format. The report also presents the performed WP6 activities since the last deliverable iteration (D6.1, M3) and communication impacts/ metrics measurement.

After the introduction, this deliverable is divided in the following sections:

- Communication and Dissemination Strategy for the period from M3 - M12.
- Communication Tools and Channels that were utilised for the promotion and dissemination of the project outputs.
- Communication Actions that were undertaken (or in the pipeline) to support each work package and implement the above mentioned Communication and Dissemination Strategy.
- Cross-Promotion and Networking: activities undertaken to establish collaboration synergies with other initiatives.
- Action plan: planning of specific actions and understanding of the relevant timings for communication as well as the responsible partners.
- Monitoring and evaluation: a set of KPIs to monitor the implementation of promotion and communication strategy.

2. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION STRATEGY (M3 - M12 OBJECTIVES)

Social and Technological Innovation Factory for Low-Carbon and Circular Industrial Value Chains - SoTecln Factory is a project funded by the European Commission’s Horizon Europe programme. The consortium led by INESC TEC, and composed by 5 other European partners (F6S, bwcon, Impact Hub HUB, Metabolic Ventures and CNR), teamed up to achieve their common mission for a more sustainable and resilient industry by connecting it to mission-based social innovators. Moreover, the project offers a **3.3 million EUR equity-free fund and capacity-building support to social innovations that improve the circularity of key product value chains by implementing higher value “Rs”,** i.e., Refuse, Rethink, Reduce, Reuse, Repair, Refurbish, Remanufacture.

Figure 1: SoTecln Factory Roadmap, as featured in the Glossary website section

To support the consortium in achieving the project objectives, SoTecln Factory communication team has devised a communication and dissemination strategy and implemented it jointly with all partners to ensure the visibility of the project among its target audience and the successful outcome of each work package output. The strategy consists of following steps:

Figure 2: SoTecln Factory communication and dissemination strategy in steps

As part of D6.1, SoTecln Factory has undertaken the task of identifying the key stakeholders and defining the specific and tailored messages and actions for each stakeholder profile (D6.1 sections Target Audience and Key Messages). For the period between M3 and M12, the Communication and Dissemination Strategy was implemented with the following communication objectives in mind:

Figure 3: SoTecln Factory goals and outputs as the basis of communication objectives

Table 1: Communication objective 1

Promotion of the Mission-based, Open-Innovation approach to systemic venture building	
Key Activities to communicate/disseminate:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The activities of the 7 regional-multi stakeholders communities convened by the Regional Hubs (Selection of regional value chains and regional workshops, formation of industry value chain-based missions) • The formation and activities of the regional Mission Councils (Open Call for Mission Councils) • The identification and selection of the value chain challenges (Open Call for Challenge Owners; Dissemination of selected Challenges)
Target Audience:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Industry Players (Industrial and technological companies) • Academia, industry and civil society (Scientists, industry leaders, NGOs, activists and civil servants focused on circular economy innovative business models, social innovation, technology innovation) • National and regional/local governments and public authorities
Tools and Channels:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industry associations, clusters, social media and news. • Peer-learning, demo actions, training, events (workshops) dialogue, project partnership.
Key Messages:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engage with the SoTecln Factory where you can aggregate knowledge, participate, and influence the development of

	<p>social innovation concepts/ products or services, with capacity to generate high economic, social, and ecological impacts.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SoTecln Factory provides you access to tech-savvy innovators capable of developing concepts/solutions to today's challenges to help your organisation become more resilient and sustainable, including leading support methodologies and tools.
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Table 2: Communication objective 2

Promotion of social innovation based on steward-ownership and SoTecln Factory social entrepreneurship support	
Key Activities to communicate/disseminate:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open Call 1 for Social Innovators
Target Audience:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tech-Savvy Innovators (startups, SMEs and NGOs) who are social impact and market oriented, have a clear business strategy and are full of enthusiasm to develop a new product, but their resources are frequently limited.
Tools and Channels:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accelerators, incubators and business associations, tech-transfer offices, hackathons and start-up events, social media, training, and peer-learning.
Key Messages:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SoTecln Factory supports mission-driven social innovation ventures in leading industry towards circular economy transition through sustainable actions (e.g., higher R strategies) • SoTecln Factory offers unique and leading methodologies and tools for entrepreneurship, from business model innovation to steward ownership. • SoTecln Factory offers access to a social innovation driven incubation programme, up to €100k non-equity funding and the opportunity to collaborate with industry and relevant stakeholders with the aim of delivering an experiment. • Join the SoTecln ecosystem and exploit new market opportunities.

Table 3: Communication objective 3

General awareness of the sustainable industry transformation through systemic change in industrial value chains.	
Key Activities to communicate/disseminate:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publication of public deliverables and scientific publications by project partners (D2.2; D2.3) • Promotion of sustainable industry and SoTecln Factory approach to systems thinking concepts
Target Audience:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • all from above
Tools and Channels:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social media, news (website and media outlets), scientific journals and conferences.
Key Messages:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthening the resilience and sustainability of your local industries is critical to ensure long-term sustainability, jobs, and economic growth. • Connect with SoTecln Factory to know more about how you can better support your local industry.

3. COMMUNICATION TOOLS AND CHANNELS

This section describes communication tools and channels used to achieve the above mentioned communication objectives.

3.1. Promotional Materials

The SoTecln Factory communication team has developed a suite of ‘Communication Materials’ (CM) at M3 (and has described it in D6.1) to facilitate the communication and dissemination for both virtual and physical engagements. The first set of marketing materials has been publicly available on the project website (section [Resources](#)) as part of the [The SoTecln Factory Media Kit](#), which also presents the project logo, brand manual, branded visuals for social media, merchandising with relevant quotes or logo and SoTecln Factory Mission Councils Factsheet.

Furthermore, the second set of marketing materials has been produced to promote the Open Call for tech-savvy innovators in the following manner:

- [Online flyer serving as a “factsheet” for the Open Call](#)
- [Rollup](#)
- [Updated Pitch presentation providing “project and Open call at glance” overview](#)

Figure 4: Screenshot of the SoTecln Factory online Flyer

Figure 5: Screenshot of the SoTecln Factory rollup

Figure 6: Screenshot of the SoTecln Factory pitch presentation

3.1.1. Animated Video

Animated video is currently under development and it is to be released as part of the promotional material for the Open Call for Social innovators promotion. The video content is aimed at explaining social innovation within the domain of circularity by showcasing the project objectives and milestones achieved so far, alongside the summary of SoTecln Factory Open Call and support programme for social innovators.

3.2. Virtual Presence

Virtual presence of the SoTecln Factory project ensures greater outreach to focal stakeholders. The following channels are utilised to create high impact online:

- Project website
- Social media

- Partners channels and platforms
- F6S platform

3.2.1. Project website

The SoTecIn Factory website has been available from M1 on www.sotecinfactory.eu. The website is designed in a way to introduce the project, as well as to provide all relevant, up-to-date information to the main target audience and the general public. It is connected to the other communication tools such as the F6S platform and social networks by serving as their main support system and information repository.

Figure 7: Screenshot of the SoTecIn Factory home page

The SoTecIn Factory website performance is monitored through following metrics:

- Conversion rates x acquisition channels
- Unique visitors
- New user x return user engagement
- Bounce rate
- Demographics

The following figures represent the status of the website metrics at the time of D6.2 submission.

Figure 8: SoTecIn Factory website overview statistics

Total Visitors	4,224
New Visitors (58.27%)	2,862
Returning Visitors (41.73%)	2,050
Total Page Views	10,634
Total Sessions	4,912

Figure 9: SoTecIn Factory website visitors statistics

MOST PAGE VIEWS	
/	3,415 (31.9%)
/the-project/	973 (9.1%)
/open-calls/	923 (8.6%)
/missions/	861 (8.0%)
/community/	652 (6.1%)
/open-calls/open-call-for-challenge-owners/	628 (5.9%)
/meet-the-team/	513 (4.8%)
/resources/	286 (2.7%)

Figure 10: SoTecIn Factory website page views statistics

Figure 11: SoTecIn Factory website traffic sources

AUDIENCE ENGAGEMENT METRICS	
Bounce Rate	62.03%
Average Session Duration	1.9 mins
Pages Per Session	2.1
Returning Visitors	40.4%

Figure 12: SoTecIn Factory website bounce rate statistics

TOP COUNTRIES		TOP CITIES	
Portugal	571 (11.6%)	(not set)	572 (11.6%)
Netherlands	415 (8.4%)	Amsterdam	256 (5.2%)
Germany	410 (8.3%)	Budapest	241 (4.9%)
Hungary	373 (7.6%)	Dublin	240 (4.9%)
United States	341 (6.9%)	Bucharest	214 (4.4%)
Romania	340 (6.9%)	Novi Sad	180 (3.7%)
Türkiye	334 (6.8%)	Lisbon	177 (3.6%)
Italy	329 (6.7%)	Istanbul	173 (3.5%)

Figure 13: SoTecln Factory website visitor demographics statistics

3.2.2. Social media

SoTecln Factory has been present from M1 in the following social networks, to increase the visibility of the SoTecln Factory community-building activities and results, but also to generate traffic to the application forms:

- [LinkedIn](#) - SoTecln Factory
- [Twitter](#) - @sotecinfactory
- [Instagram](#) - @sotecinfactory
- [YouTube](#) - sotecinfactory

All project channels combined, SoTecln Factory has amassed 453 followers against the KPI of 1500 followers until the end of the project.

3.2.2.1. LinkedIn Page

SoTecln Factory LinkedIn page proves to be the most effective channel for communicating with target audiences. The following figures represent the LinkedIn metrics in the period from the launch of the project account (1 July 2022) until the moment of D6.2 submission.

Figure 14: Screenshot of SoTecln Factory LinkedIn activity overview

FOLLOWER METRICS	
All-time Followers [?]	308
Followers Gained	288
Organic Followers Gained	288
Paid Followers Gained	0

Figure 15: Screenshot of SoTecln Factory LinkedIn followers metrics

ENGAGEMENT METRICS - JUL 2022		IMPRESSIONS METRICS	
Likes	443	Total Impressions	21,623
Comments	3	Average Daily Impressions	65
Shares	118		
Clicks	976		
Total Engagements	1,540		

Figure 16: Screenshot of SoTecln Factory LinkedIn engagement & impressions metrics

Figure 17: Screenshot of SoTecln Factory LinkedIn demographics metrics per type of stakeholder

BY COUNTRY		BY COMPANY SIZE	
Portugal	53	Between 11 and 50	70
Netherlands	36	Between 2 and 10	43
Germany	28	Between 51 and 200	33
Italy	27	Between 1001 and 5000	32
Serbia	23	Between 10001 and infinity	19
Belgium	13	Between 201 and 500	16
Romania	13	Between 5001 and 10000	10
Spain	11	Between 501 and 1000	8

Figure 18: Screenshot of SoTecln Factory LinkedIn demographics metrics per country of origin

3.2.2.2. Twitter Page

The following figures represent the Twitter metrics in the period from the launch of the project account (1 July 2022) until the moment of D6.2 submission.

Figure 19: Screenshot of SoTecln Factory Twitter activity overview

FOLLOWER METRICS	
Total Followers	59
Followers Gained	59
Total You Follow	75
People You Followed	75

Figure 20: Screenshot of SoTecln Factory Twitter followers metrics

ENGAGEMENT METRICS	
Mentions	9
Retweets	21
Likes	91
Tweets Sent	65
Total Engagements	121

Figure 21: Screenshot of SoTecln Factory Twitter engagement metrics

Figure 22: Screenshot of SoTecIn Factory Twitter demographics metrics

3.2.2.3. Instagram Page

The following figures represent the Instagram metrics in the period from the launch of the project account (1 July 2022) until the moment of D6.2 submission.

Figure 23: Screenshot of the SoTecIn Factory Instagram followers metrics

Figure 24: Screenshot of the SoTecIn Factory Instagram engagement metrics

3.2.2.4. YouTube Page

So far, the SoTecIn Factory Youtube Page has gained 2 subscribers and had one video uploaded([SoTecIn Factory Open Call for Challenge Owners Webinar](#)) , with 8 views and one comment.

Figure 25: Screenshot of the SoTeCin Factory YouTube page

3.2.3. Partners Channels

Existing networks of all consortium members play an essential role in reaching the target audiences. Additionally, each participating social innovator will also use their networks and social media channels to share their experiences, gather information and to promote the project. Each partner is responsible for reaching out to their partner organisations and intermediaries to promote the project activities and events, as well as the Open Calls.

Table 4: SoTeCin Factory Partners' communication channels

Partner	Communication Channels
INESC TEC	LinkedIn: INESC TEC Technology and Science -Associate Laboratory Twitter: @INESCTEC Instagram: @inesctec YouTube: INESC TEC
bwcon	LinkedIn: bwcon Twitter: @bwcon_info YouTube: bwcon Newsletter: https://www.bwcon.de/newsletter
Metabolic	LinkedIn: Metabolic Twitter: @MetabolicHQ Instagram: @metabolichq Newsletter: https://www.metabolic.nl/contact-us/
Impact Hub	LinkedIn: Impact Hub Twitter: @impacthub Instagram: @impacthub YouTube: Impact Hub Newsletter: http://eepurl.com/dG7HWP
CNR	LinkedIn: Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche

	Twitter: @CNRsocial Instagram: @ieit_cnr YouTube: CNR-IEIT
F6S	LinkedIn: F6S Innovation Twitter: @F6S_Gov Project page: coming soon (occasion of the Open Calls)

3.2.4. F6S Platform

The project's Open Calls are hosted on the F6S platform (www.f6s.com).

The project is presented in following F6S pages:

- [SoTecln Factory F6S Page](#)
- [SoTecln Factory Challenge Owners Call](#)
- [Open Call for Social Innovators](#)
- [Evaluators Express of Interest](#)

The SoTecln Factory pages on F6S follow the visual identity of the project and they are integrated with the project website and social media. The pages also include a forum where interested applicants are able to ask questions to the consortium.

3.3 Physical Presence (Events)

Physical Presence of the project at the external events has been identified as one of the key ways of promoting SoTecln Factory, with the KPI of 20-30 events attended on an international level (conferences, seminars, workshops) being set up in the Grant Agreement.

As of May 2023, SoTecln Factory has been promoted in the following events:

1. [PRO-VE2022, 20 September 2022 at Lisbon, Portugal](#), where SoTecln Factory was presented by project partner CNR as part of the panel called "Society5.0 -how to offer integrated services to citizens?"

Figure 26: SoTecln Factory at PRO-VE2022, 20 September 2022 at Lisbon, Portugal

2. [TechChill Conference](#), 27-29 September 2022 in Milano, Italy, where SoTecln Factory was presented by project partner F6S to the social innovation startup community.

Figure 27: SoTeCin Factory at TechChill Milano, 27 - 29 September, 2022 in Milano, Italy

3. [Food and Water Sustainability Business Forum in Budapest, Hungary, October 4, 2022](#) during which Impact Hub Budapest has presented the project to key stakeholders such as ingredient producers, water technology manufacturers, buyers, academia, professionals and investors from the CEE region in order to enhance cooperation, share knowledge and promote innovation.

Figure 28: Food and Water Sustainability Business Forum in Budapest, Hungary, October 4, 2022

4. [Circular bioeconomy a shift towards sustainable food production, 13 - 14 October 2022 in Tartu, Estonia](#) - international scientific conference lead by Ministry of Rural Affairs of Estonia at which Impact Hub Budapest has promoted the project to agriculture ministers of EaP and EU countries.

Figure 29: Circular bioeconomy a shift towards sustainable food production, 13 -14 October 2022, Tartu, Estonia

5. [II. REL EXPO - smart solutions for the short supply chain in Kaposvár, Hungary, 10 November 2022](#) - organised by Kislépték Egyesület during which Impact Hub Budapest has promoted SoTeCin Factory and interacted with agrifood producers, market organisers, rural developers, cooperatives,

suppliers, consultants, restaurants and traders using local produce, local authorities, LEADER organisations, consultants, gardeners.

Figure 30: II. REL EXPO - smart solutions for the short supply chain in Kaposvár, Hungary, 10 November 2022

6. [HunBAN Year Starter Pitch Night at EIT Digital Budapest CLC - 22 February 2023](#) - networking event organised by Hungarian Business Angel Network during which Impact Hub Budapest has promoted the project to angel aspirants, startup founders, VCs and angels.

7. [EIT Food](#) open innovation call collaboration models and [SoTecIn Factory](#) Program information webinar on March 7, 2023 at an online meeting for [Türkiye Gıda İnovasyon Platformu | TÜGİP](#) members (presented by Impact Hub Istanbul).

Figure 31: SoTecIn Factory Programme information webinar at TÜGİP, Türkiye Gıda İnovasyon Platformu, March 7,2023.

8. [TalentA Hungary, 27 April 2023 \(online\)](#) - training & mentoring program organised by Corteva Agriscience during which Impact Hub Budapest promoted the project to attendees interested in improving their leadership skills, business, financial and agricultural knowledge with the support of renowned experts.

3.4 Media

To ensure the proper project visibility, SoTeIn Factory has been promoted in the relevant media outlets, with the stated KPI of minimum 6 media releases being successfully surpassed with web articles in 12 Portuguese media outlets, all being accessible in the [SoTeIn Factory in Media](#) website section covering project related press articles.

Table 5: List of published web articles until May 2023

Title	Author	Date	URL
Projecto SoTeIn Factory vai financiar ideias de inovação social, incluindo na área de construção e edifícios	Edifícios e Energia Online	25/07/2022	http://www.pt.cision.com/s/?l=de661ba3
Projeto apoia soluções para reduzir pegada de carbono na indústria	Indústria e Ambiente Online	27/07/2022	http://www.pt.cision.com/s/?l=c05dbdd2
Projeto europeu tem 3 milhões de euros para tornar indústrias mais sustentáveis	Alimentar Online	22/07/2022	http://www.pt.cision.com/s/?l=858bb90e
Projeto europeu tem 3 milhões de euros para tornar indústrias mais sustentáveis	Revista O Instalador Online	22/07/2022	http://www.pt.cision.com/s/?l=aa7dce1f
Projeto liderado pelo INESC TEC vai apoiar com 3,3 milhões de euros soluções para reduzir pegada de carbono na indústria	Água & Ambiente Online	22/07/2022	http://www.pt.cision.com/s/?l=8e7172cd
Projeto europeu liderado pelo INESC TEC tem 3 milhões de euros para tornar indústrias mais sustentáveis	Executive Digest Online	21/07/2022	http://www.pt.cision.com/s/?l=89bde83d
Projeto europeu tem três milhões para tornar indústrias mais sustentáveis	Jornal Económico Online (O)	21/07/2022	http://www.pt.cision.com/s/?l=5a62907c

Projeto vai apoiar soluções para reduzir pegada de carbono na indústria	Notícias ao Minuto Online	21/07/2022	http://www.pt.cision.com/s/?l=caab077
Projeto vai apoiar com 3,3 milhões de euros soluções para reduzir pegada de carbono na indústria	Observador Online	21/07/2022	http://www.pt.cision.com/s/?l=3810dc31

3.5 News and Articles

To regularly share news and relevant content with its community, SoTecln Factory has implemented the following activities:

SoTecln Factory Newsletter

So far, the project newsletter has been released twice, on February 10, 2023, and on March 20, 2023. It currently has 166 subscribers. Visitors to the website can subscribe to the SoTecln newsletter, as well as read the past editions (see [Newsletter Section](#)). The following figures represent newsletter statistics of the first two editions:

The 1st Edition, February 10, 2023. [\(read here\)](#)

Figure 32: Newsletter statistics of the 1st edition (February 10, 2023.)

The 2nd Edition, March 20, 2023. ([read here](#))

145 Recipients

Audience: Sotecin Factory

Delivered: Mon, Mar 20, 2023 7:34 am

Subject: The SoTecln Factory 2nd Newsletter Edition is Out!

[View email](#) · [Download](#) · [Print](#) · [Share](#)

Figure 33: Newsletter statistics of the 2nd edition (March 20, 2023.)

SoTecln Factory press releases

Project press releases are being developed during relevant occasions of the project, to be shared with local and international media such as relevant electronic business media and printed press. These press releases follow a certain format, including a description of the project in general to raise awareness of the project, as well as the current news and information designed to follow each crucial stage of the project. So far 2 press releases have been published in the format of website blog posts:

[The 1st Press Release \(29 June, 2022\)](#)

[The 2nd Press Release \(20 October, 2022.\)](#)

SoTecln Factory blog posts on the website

The project website has a section for **“LATEST NEWS”**, which is updated regularly with short articles about the SoTecln Factory activities and developments. It currently hosts 16 blog posts.

Figure 34: Screenshot of the SoTecln Factory Latest News section

3.6 Scientific publications

Based on the outputs from D2.1 Report on low-carbon and circular industrial value chains (CNR), the first SoTeCIn Factory scientific article will be presented at the EurOMA 2023 Conference, 3-5 July 2023, in Leuven, Belgium (<https://euroma2023.org/>):

Title: The role of R-Strategies for Circular Supply Chains - a systematic literature review

Author(s): Ines, Ana; Dalmarco, Gustavo; Zimmermann, Ricardo; Fornasiero, Rosanna

Abstract: Circular Economy discusses the replacement of the end-of-life strategy with a closed loop material flow, minimizing raw material consumption by extending the life cycle of materials. Since this approach is expanding from individual organizational actions to supply chain level policies and practices, our objective is to conduct a systematic literature review that presents the role of circular strategies in the development of circular supply chains. This paper contributes to theory and practice by: presenting a clear definition of each R-Strategy; discussing their role to the development of circular SCs; and identifying how SC actors are involved in the R processes.

This article, as well as other scientific publications will be publicly available via the project website ([Publications Section](#)) , as well as the [project community on Zenodo](#) (integrated with INESC TEC repository).

4. COMMUNICATION ACTIONS

This section represents the communication actions undertaken to support key project activities and goals, as defined for the M3-M12 communication objectives.

4.1 Actions to support each work package

4.1.1 Promotion of the selected regional value chains and regional workshops

Led by 7 Regional Hubs, which are hosted by the project partner Impact Hub (IH) and its local organisations (IH Amsterdam, IH Lisbon, IH Milan IH Bucharest, IH Budapest, IH Hamburg, and IH Istanbul), the SoTeCIn Factory Community has participated in conducting an assessment to define and select which ones of the 7 key product value chains of the [EU Circular Economy Action Plan](#) are more relevant to their specific region. As a result, the following key product value chains were selected for each one of the 7 economic regions, as listed:

1. Netherlands (North-West, including Northern France, Belgium, Luxembourg, Ireland)
 - Textiles
2. Portugal (South-West, including Spain, Southern France)
 - Food, Water and Nutrients
3. Italy (Centre-South, including Slovenia, Croatia, Malta)
 - Textiles
4. Romania (South-East, including Greece, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Serbia, Ukraine)
 - Food, Water and Nutrients
5. Hungary (North-East, including Slovakia, Poland, Estonia, Lithuania, Latvia)
 - Food, Water and Nutrients
6. Germany (Centre-North, including Denmark, Austria, Sweden, Finland)
 - Plastics and Packaging
7. Turkey (East, including Armenia and Georgia)
 - Food, Water and Nutrients

After the initial announcement via the 2nd press release on 21 October 2022, the communication team has released a blog post dedicated to each regional selection (7 in total):

Table 6: List of regional blog post announcements

Regional Hub of Centre-North selects plastics and packaging value chains for the mission of circular industry transformation (26 October 2022.)
Regional Hub of North-West selects textiles value chain for the mission of circular industry transformation (31 October 2022.)
Regional Hub of North-East selects food, water and nutrients key value chain for the mission of circular industry transformation (2 November 2022.) Regional Hub of Centre-South selects textile key value chain for their circular industry mission (9 November 2022.)
Regional Hub of East selects food, water and nutrients key value chain for their circular industry mission (29 November 2022.)

[Regional Hub of South-East selects food, water and nutrients key value chain for their circular industry mission \(7 December, 2022.\)](#)

[Regional Hub of South-West selects food, water and nutrients key value chain for their circular industry mission \(16 January 2023.\)](#)

The blog posts were structured in a way to explain the selection process and reasoning behind it, as well as to explain the next step in SoTecln Factory at that moment, which was the formulation of regional Missions based on selected value chains via participation in the regional workshops. The blog posts were therefore published (accompanied with social media visuals) to also invite the target stakeholders to the upcoming workshops.

4.1.2 Promotion of the Mission-based approach and formulated Missions as end results

Project partners Impact Hub and its 7 local hubs have held a series of online meetings aimed at attracting industrial companies, public bodies, academia and civil servants society to jointly formulate at least 7 key value chain-based missions (at least one mission per each region and its selected value chain). While the WP3 partners focused on the logistics and scouting for the regional workshops, WP6 supported their actions mainly through the workshop dissemination by posting and re-sharing the news and outcomes of the events. The communication efforts were also focused toward promoting and explaining the Mission-based approach to systemic change utilised in SoTecln Factory.

Figure 35: Screenshot examples of dissemination posts for regional workshops

Figure 36: Screenshot of the social media visual explaining the Mission-based approach

The meetings resulted in 7 formulated Missions in total, all announced via [Missions Section](#), the space on the project website dedicated to the development and progress monitoring of social innovation missions based on the Key Value Chains. Since the first iteration of this deliverable, the section has been updated to include 3 subpages, each dedicated to regional Missions of one of the selected Key Value Chains: [Food, Water & Nutrients](#), [Textiles](#) and [Plastics & Packaging](#).

Figure 37: Screenshot of the SoTecIn Factory Missions page

Formulated SoTecIn Factory missions served as the basis of the Open Call for Challenge Owners designed to help industry leaders to identify and subsequently provide mission-based sustainability challenges relevant for their organisation. To facilitate the application process for potential Challenge Owners, the communication team has utilised a dynamic approach by allowing the applicant to match their Challenge with a Mission within their value chain and region via interactive Mission Map ([see the original website blog post](#)).

Figure 38: Social Media Visual to promote the Interactive Mission Map

The Missions were afterwards explained separately through a series of visuals during the Open Call for Challenge Owners (see Table 7: Open Call for Challenge Owners Promo Brochures). However, the communication team continues their promotional storytelling in relation to the Open Call for Social Innovators to explain the circular industry visions behind Mission-based Challenges, to which the submitted Solutions should respond to.

4.1.3 Promotion of the Mission Councils

Besides engaging in the Mission selection, active Community members were also able to apply from 12 December 2022 until 15 February 2023 for the membership in regional Mission Councils, 7 multi-stakeholder groups of selected experts acting as ‘guardians’ of this broader mission, by overseeing the progression of the challenges by the challenge owners and solution providers – specifically, overseeing the development of the higher-R focused, early-stage enterprises, deployment of their solutions, and ensuring that the ventures stay focused on the overarching mission throughout the duration of the program.

Throughout the whole Open Call for Mission Councils, SoTecIn Factory website has hosted the Google application form , alongside a [Mission Councils Fact Sheet](#) produced by project partner Metabolic (as the Open Call lead), where the potential applicants could find more in-dept information about the role and benefits of the Mission Councils.

Figure 39: Screenshot of the Mission Councils Fact Sheet (produced by Metabolic Ventures)

To actively promote the Open Call, the communication team has also devised a strategy of releasing a series of visuals, as well as short video clips (lasting maximum 30 seconds) as Call to Actions explaining the role and benefits of participating in Mission Councils, both generally and specifically targeted to stakeholders from one of the selected key value chains. The Open Call for Mission Councils was also the subject of the 1st SoTecln Factory Newsletter, while Metabolic held a Mission Councils Info Session ([read the blog post](#)).

Figure 40: Open Call for Mission Councils promo material

Mission Councils Call to Action 1 (LinkedIn , Twitter)
Mission Councils Call to Action 2 (LinkedIn , Twitter)
Mission Councils: Benefits- visual series (LinkedIn , Twitter , Instagram)
Mission Councils: Role and Structure (LinkedIn , Twitter)
Mission Councils promo video clip no.1 (LinkedIn ; Twitter)
Mission Councils promo video clip no.2 (LinkedIn , Instagram)
Mission Councils promo video clip no.3 (LinkedIn , Twitter)

The Open Call for Mission Councils has resulted in 48 active council members, with 37 being featured in the [Mission Councils webpage](#), via an individual page dedicated to their short biography.

Figure 41: Screenshot and the link of the Mission Councils website section

4.1.4 Promotion of the Open Call for Challenge Owners and Challenges

Promotion of the Open Call for Challenge Owners

Led by project partner bwcon, Open Call for Challenge Owners was presented at its initial kick-off workshop on 22 February 2023 and it was open until 23 March 2023. The Open Call was hosted on the F6S platform, [Open Call for Challenge Owners](#) website subpage, served as a space for industry challenge owners featuring the guidelines for the Open Call application and the path to the F6S platform where the said application form was hosted. The page has also explained in the nutshell the role and the participation process for the Challenge Owners.

Figure 42: Screenshot of the Open Call for Challenge Owners subpage

While direct stakeholder scouting was done primarily by WP3 partners, WP6 has supported the Open Call promotion through the release of the promo brochures (one per region and its Mission(s) that were available to WP3 partners as the support material during direct stakeholder contacting, but could also act a series of stand-alone visuals, all published via social media to further explain the role and benefits of Challenge Owners, as well as the specific Missions to which their Challenges should be based on. The following table contains the social media links of described brochures (the source from the project LinkedIn account):

Table 7: Open Call for Challenge Owners promo brochures

Open Call for Challenge Owners: Promo Brochure 1
Open Call for Challenge Owners: Promo Brochure 2
Open Call for Challenge Owners: Promo Brochure 3
Open Call for Challenge Owners: Promo Brochure 4
Open Call for Challenge Owners: Promo Brochure 5
Open Call for Challenge Owners: Promo Brochure 6

The second SoTeCn Factory newsletter edition was fully dedicated to the promotion of the Open Call for Challenge Owners, while the video recording of SoTeCn Factory Open Call for Challenge Owners webinar held by bwcon (and attended by 30 participants) is available [on the project YouTube channel](#).

Promotion of selected Challenges

The Open Call for Challenge Owners has resulted in 38 applications and 21 selected Challenges. For promotional purposes, all selected challenges, and their respective “Owners”, are listed in [Challenge Owners website page](#), as part of the [Community Section](#) (which also stores the summarized information and access to each sub-page).

Figure 43: Screenshot and the link of the Challenge Owners website section

During the Open Call for Social Innovators, the social media campaigns will be utilised to facilitate the understanding of each type of challenge that the applicants would potentially choose to respond to.

4.1.5 Promotion of the other project results

Dissemination of D2.2

Project partner Impact Hub has produced a public deliverable [D2.2 Final Guidelines “Principles for mission oriented social innovation through a stewardship model”](#) with the intention is to enable diverse stakeholders to better understand the innovativeness of the SoTeCn Factory space, dynamics and goals and thus open up opportunities for the innovation process to be successful and meaningful.

To successfully disseminate D2.2, the communication team has produced a discussion blog post titled [“Purpose, not just profit! How to achieve a sustainable impact in the industry via a steward-ownership model? ”](#) to introduce the readers to the steward-ownership principles and the SoTeCn Factory approach to this governance model and alternative company ownership.

Figure 44: Visuals used to promote D2.2 discussion blog post

Furthermore, the communication team has utilised the existing [Glossary website section](#) to support the stakeholders in researching “Sustainable Industry Transformation 101” basics, while D2.2 serves as the complementary source for in-depth explanation of each listed concept and process.

4.1.6 General promotion of the sustainable industry transformation

Besides focusing on the project activities, the communication team has been using a storytelling approach to introduce the main project activities and goal, as well as the partners’ involvement in the following format:

- Discussion blog posts
- Infographic visuals (#circularityconversations for sustainable industry visual explanations aimed at stirring online conversation among stakeholders).

Figure 45: Screenshot example of the SoTeIn Factory discussion blog post ([click here to read](#))

Figure 46: Screenshot example of the SoTeIn Factory [#circularityconversations](#) visuals [\(go to LinkedIn source\)](#)

“GLOSSARY” website section has been utilised as a repository for all definitions of SoTeIn Factory key actors and elements of the project activities (“[SoTeIn Factory A to Z](#)” section), as well as the “[Sustainable Industry Transformation 101](#)”, a list of the most relevant circular economy and social innovation terms, explained to the project audiences, to facilitate the understanding of the project.

Figure 47: Screenshot of the “[Sustainable Industry Transformation 101](#)” visual [\(go to LinkedIn source\)](#)

4.2 Actions to support the social media campaign to engage SoTecln Factory Tech-savvy innovators

The main project focus in the upcoming period is the promotion of the Open Call 1 for Social Innovators who will choose to engage in the SoTecln Factory funding and support programme for Mission-based sustainable industry solutions.

F6S as T3.4 leader will deploy a strong Open Call recruiting campaign which includes i) scouting across EU for tech-savvy innovators; ii) activating networks and social innovation agencies; iii) participating & (co-) organizing promotion events; iv) deployment of 2 info webinars per call. WP6, on the other hand, will support T3.4 and the general Open Call promotion, firstly by establishing a dedicated Open Call website subpage to easily navigate the traffic to the F6S application form, and secondly by harnessing the power of social media in spreading the news.

To systematically implement the Open Call communication strategy, as well as support the other WP3 partners in their promotional efforts, the communication team will engage in the following activities:

- i. Project/networks/events mapping to assess industry/EU networks and other social innovation-driven organisations as the main intermediaries when promoting the project. In addition, the mapping process includes utilising the established Networking and Events Calendar of both internal and external events to facilitate the project dissemination.
- ii. Development of the programme value proposition (Open Call summary) as the base for the marketing strategy and the Open Call process.
- iii. Development of the Open Call promotion kit to support project partners in the communication of the SoTecln Factory project under the same branding instructions.

Project/networks/events mapping

To further boost and facilitate the promotion of the project via physical presence, SoTecln Factory has produced a Networking and Events calendar to complement the Tech-savvy innovators' interaction, with the "External Events" spreadsheet being divided into 6-months periods. The initial iteration, which was produced in M3 and described in D6.1, has contained 23 external events mapped for the first 12 months of the project. Since then, 17 new events (as showcased in table down below) were added to the list, as the potential venues to promote Open Call 1 for Social Innovators and the support programme in general.

Table 8: List of potential events for Open Call 1 promotion

Techsylvania
ITMA
Planet Textiles: Sustainable Textiles Summit
Hinterland of Things
PLASTICS RECYCLING WORLD EXPO EUROPE 2023
We Make Future
The Next Web

Viva Technology
NBM2023
Webit Summer Edition
Pirate Summit
Climate action and the accountancy profession
International Conference on Sustainability Change Management - (ICSCMAN-23)
Regenerative Agriculture and Food Systems Summit Europe
Programul Antreprenor în Agricultură 4.0
BASF Innovation Hub
Impact Growth Smart Agrifood

The same excel base, which provides an overview of the main types of identified potential collaborators (other running projects, initiatives, business networks and associations) will also be used to support T3.4 leaders in scouting activities especially when implementing the promotional strategy for boosting the Open Call outreach via intermediaries.

The outcome of the Open Call promotion will be detailed in the upcoming Communication Plan and Progress deliverable iterations D6.3 (due Month 24) and D6.4 (due Month 36).

The programme value proposition (Open Call Summary)

It will be defined jointly by project partners, and it represents a document translating Open Call benefits into easy-to-read and commercial language bullet points. It is designed in a way to showcase the main goals and offers, as well as target stakeholders of the programme. In addition, the document systemically represents the summary of the whole programme based on the main Open Call concepts and documents (i.e., Open Call guide for applicants, Open Call Text, application form).

The Open Call promotional kit

The promotion of the SoTeIn Factory funding opportunity and systemic acceleration programme will primarily be done on the project communication channels. However, the consortium partners will also be supported in spreading the Open Call news in a unified, branded manner via the Open Call promotion kit available for all partners to utilise. The partners will be provided with the instructions by F6S, the Open Call Kit creator, in a single document linking to all materials needed to promote Open Call:

- The Link to the project website / Open Call subpage/ the F6S platform
- The press release
- Social media visuals (access to the repository folder) and social media copy examples
- Pitch-deck (PowerPoint) presentation
- Open Call Summary (a short PDF document containing hyperlinked PowerPoint slides with commercial text and visual illustrations)
- Email template for intermediaries (e.g., relevant industry networks and press/media organisations)

5. CROSS-PROMOTION AND NETWORKING

SoTeIn Factory is working on creating a strong network in the business communities to prepare the EU industry transition journey. To achieve that, SoTeIn Factory intends to establish synergies with other running projects, initiatives, business networks and associations as well as specific platforms and EU agencies with the aim of involving them during project implementation. The success of such actions will be validated by the number of collaboration agreements with existing initiatives (target KPI: 5) and joint campaigns (target KPI: 3), as defined in the Grant Agreement.

The strategy envisioned for the creation of synergies includes the following steps:

1. **Identification of key initiatives and assessment of collaboration opportunities**
2. **Engagement of the initiatives (contacting and networking)**
3. **Communication of results and recording of evidence**
4. **Assessment of results and identification of further synergies**

5.1 Key Identified Initiatives

Created at the beginning of the project, a Networking and Events calendar has been regularly updated to provide an overview of the main types of potential collaborators, as they were identified at the proposal stage and through subsequent collaboration of the communication team with project partners via the SoTeIn Factory initial communication questionnaire in the following manner

1. **Industry Networks/ EU initiatives**, which covers prominent industry networks such as industry associations, clusters and DIHs, as well as related EU projects and EU initiatives, specifically national competence centres for social innovation funded by the EU in part through the 2014-2020 European Social Fund and the EU programme for Employment and Social Innovation (EaSI). At the moment, the spreadsheet contains 110 stakeholders covering all three industrial value chains targeted by the project (food, water & nutrients, textiles, plastics & packaging).
2. **Acceleration Programmes**, with the current list of 35 relevant accelerators and incubators
3. **Research and Academia**, showcasing 44 universities and research centres which are well connected with the project partners
4. **Media Outlets**, with 35 sources identified so far.

5.2 Types of Synergies

Collaboration agreements provide mutual opportunities, but also ensure obligations towards the collaborator. The services would be tailored to different initiatives, but the overall action plan would cover the following activities:

1. Cross-promotion and dissemination

This type of cooperation is applicable for each identified type of initiative, and it includes the following opportunities:

- Mutual promotion via website blog posts and social media platforms.
- Appearance in promotional materials (visuals, banners and videos).
- Reporting via press releases and newsletter editions.

2. Event coordination

Event organization could go two ways: SoTecln Factory is willing to participate in the organization and promotion of other networks' events while providing collaborators with the chance to take an active role in SoTecln Factory events, most importantly in cross-European mash-ups and workshops, otherwise pivotal moments for connecting the vast community of stakeholders from multiple countries.

3. Mentor-jury exchange

Another fruitful opportunity for social innovators-oriented organizations which would facilitate the evaluation and capacity building process of programme participants.

4. Connection and Networking with Community Members

This opportunity allows SoTecln Factory Collaborators to get in touch with 300+ industry, academia, NGOs and public sector members across 7 economic regions which SoTecln Factory has successfully brought together to design shared key value chain-based missions in a bottom-up manner, prevent the Mission drift as one of the Mission Councils members, but to also directly seek a Mission-based innovative solution for a challenge within their organisation as one of the Challenge Owners. Furthermore, with the establishment of the SoTecln Factory Online Community, the collaborators will be able to directly communicate and share sustainable industry news and knowledge with its members. In return for being able to promote their own activities in the SoTecln Factory communication groups, the project consortium would request the admission of the SoTecln Factory to the collaborators' networks.

5.3 Communication of Results and Recording of Evidence

The main tools which SoTecln Factory would use to further promote collaboration agreements would encompass joint dissemination campaigns in several languages; success stories through website, social media; partners' communication channels (websites, newsletters, blogs, emailing lists, magazines, etc.), relevant electronic business media and printed press, communication channels, as well as promotion via business articles in relevant electronic business media and printed press.

5.4 Assessments of Results and Identification of further Synergies

The effectiveness of collaborations will be monitored and utilized as a navigator for further pursuit of the proven synergy tactics. The outcomes of the collaboration agreements and campaigns will be closely followed and reported in the upcoming WP6 deliverables related to Communication Plan and Progress (D6.2 , D6.3 and D6.4).

5.5. Collaboration Action Plan for the next period

The internal discussion that is currently underway with several initiatives is focused on closing the collaboration agreements that would enable fruitful promotion of the Open Call for Social Innovators, but also successful identification of external evaluators and industry experts as mentors of the SoTecln Factory funding and support programme.

6. ACTION PLAN

6.1 Project Timeline

The SoTeIn Factory stakeholder engagement strategy envisioned in the Grant Agreement is divided into three different phases of engagement: **BUILDING**, **PILOTING** and **USING**.

Figure 48: SoTeIn Factory communication timeline

The first phase of the project, which lasted until M12, (M1-M12) ensured the proper awareness raising and initial engagement of the relevant stakeholders while helping to create a strong network in the business communities to prepare the EU industry transition journey. Overlapping from M6 with the first phase, the piloting phase (M6-M30) focuses on the information, mobilisation and presentation of industry players, tech-savvy innovators and relevant stakeholders which takes place via the SoTeIn Factory project’s online platform, and F6S, leveraging state-of-the-art communication processes, channels that reach relevant stakeholders and enforce the importance of innovations that combine technological and social innovation to overcome challenges associated with low-carbon and circular industrial value chains. The scopes are to build a supportive environment for tech-savvy innovators, engage the stakeholders to specific actions and campaigns, continue communication and storytelling on and for innovators, spread and promote specific actions/results (collaborative ecosystems, resilience & sustainability, social innovation, open calls, hackathons, events, webinars, etc.) to specific audience (industry, innovators, startups, SMEs, and others), follow the transition journey of industries with tailored and regularly updated communication tools – stories in blogs, videos, infographics, business articles, etc.

6.2 Piloting Phase Action Plan (M12 - M24)

The following table represents the ideas for the communication activities during the piloting phase:

Table 9: Building Phase timeline

M12-M16 (May - September 2023)

- The set of materials to announce the Open Call 1 for Social Innovators
- Recruitment and scouting campaign for tech-savvy social innovators (Info Webinars/General Social Media Promotion)

- Announcement of the selected social innovators
- Launch of the SoTecln Factory Online Community
- D2.4 Report on Impact assessment framework
- D2.3 Report with new business models

M17 - M24 (October 2023 - March 2024)

- D2.2 Report on low-carbon and circular industrial value chains
- Dissemination of the progress and the results of the Deployment Phase 1
- Promotion of the Phase 2 to select 15 tech-savvy innovators
- Promotion of the Open Call 2 for Social Innovators

6.3 SoTecln Factory Online Community: Launch and Promotion

The Sotecin Factory Community is shaping up, with 7 regional hubs which have already connected with +300 relevant stakeholders for various activities (choosing the value chain, defining the missions, engaging as Mission Council members or interested in becoming Challenge Owners). So far the community was an informal one, each regional hub kept in contact locally, via email, webinars or 1 to 1 calls.

The community will further grow with the tech savvy innovators who will apply with solutions in the following open calls and also with other relevant stakeholders, to reach the KPI by the end of the project.

In order to increase the engagement and impact of the community and the cross-polenization between regions and other similar project, we set up a more formal community in the form of a LinkedIn group called [Innovative Minds: SoTecln Factory Community](#), where we will invite all stakeholders mentioned above and offer opportunities for growth, learning and sharing. The platform was chosen to ensure efficient budget spending as it is an open, free platform and to reach the right audience, as it is a professional platform.

The community of like minded people, interested in tech driven sustainability will remain open for others to join, thus contributing to the dissemination of the project results.

While WP3 partners are leading the online community strategy, WP6 will support them in the LinkedIn group promotion and dissemination activities.

Figure 49: SoTecln Factory Online Community (LinkedIn group) visual to be used for promotion

7. MONITORING AND EVALUATION (COMMUNICATION KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS)

The series of indicators were defined at the proposal stage to assess the progress of the communication efforts. The table below presents the progress of the communication efforts at the moment of the D6.2 submission through Key Point Indicators predefined in the Description of the Action.

Table 10: SoTecIn Factory KPIs

Specific C&D measures	Metric	Target KPI	Achieved so far	WP
SoTecIn Factory Community	No. members of the online community	+600	+300 in regional hub communities	3
	No. participants to mash-ups	+150	+250	3
	No. people in multi stakeholder communities	+100	TBD	3
Event participation (with social innovators and companies)	No. events attended on international level (conferences, seminars, workshops)	20-30	8	3-4-5
	No. attendees	+700	+100	
Project website/ dashboard	Unique visits by the end of the project	30,000	4,912	6
F6S Platform	Open Call applicants (tech-savvy innovators)	Min. 200	TBD	3
Social Media (LinkedIn, Twitter, Instagram, YouTube)	Followers	1500	453	6
Media/ press visibility	Appearance in business magazines, web articles, newspapers	Min. 6	12	6
Synergies with existing networks	Collaboration agreements	5	TBD	3,6
	Joint Campaigns	3	TBD	3,6

8. CONCLUSION

This report has provided the overview of the SoTeIn Factory communication and dissemination strategy alongside accompanying communication channels & tools and implementation actions that were utilised and undertaken for the period from M3 - M12 of the project.

As described, the communication and dissemination strategy of the project will be continuously monitored and improved throughout the project, according to the needs identified. As such, the Communication Plan and Progress deliverable updates are envisioned to continue in its iterations D6.3 (due Month 24) and D6.4 (due Month 36).